

RNA22 v2 results

Results have been computed and are shown below. If there are no results shown, it means your chosen parameters yielded no results.

Note: The p-value represents the likelihood that the target site loci is random. That is, a lower p-value represents a greater chance that the loci contains a valid MRE

miR Name	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	482	-22.30	CGTTCGGATGCTCGAACTGCACC : TGGTCTCTACG--TCGTGACGTGG	3.81E-2
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	8102	-12.00	GTTGCAACTGCAGAGCTGAACT : : TGGTCTCTACGTC-GTGACGTGG	6.2E-2
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	10168	-18.60	TCCAAGACATGTG-ATCTGCACC : TGGT-CTCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	2.65E-1
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	11819	-15.30	TGTATCAAAGTAGCCACTGTACA : : TGGTCTCTACGTCG-TGACGTGG	2.39E-1
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	13357	-13.86	ACTTAAAAACACAGT-CTGTACC : : : TGG-TCTCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	1.59E-1
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	14571	-14.40	CCCTGCTATGCA-CGCTGCTTC : : TGGTCTCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	2.46E-1
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	14620	-15.50	ACGTGCTTTTCAGTAGTGCACT : : TGGTCTCTACGTCGT-GACGTGG	3.2E-1
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	16926	-16.60	TACAGTAATGCCATTAAGTGCACC TGGTCTCTACG--TCGTGACGTGG	8.01E-2
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	16936	-13.90	CCATTAAGTGCA-C-CTACACT : : TGGTCTCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	8.01E-2
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	20995	-12.70	GGTGATTGTGCA--ACTGTACA : : TGGTCTCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	7.09E-2
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	23397	-19.90	ATCAG-GATGT-TAACTGCACA : TGGTCTCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	1.01E-1
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	24043	-14.50	ACTTGCAGATGC-TGGCTTCATC : : : TGGTCTCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	1.04E-1
hsa_mir_143	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	29172	-12.50	ATTGG--CCGCA-AATTGCACA : : TGGTCTCTACGTCGTGACGTGG	6.2E-2

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let_7a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	485	-14.00	TCGGATGCTCGAACTGC -ACCTCA : : TTGATATG - TTGGATGATGGAGT	3.81E-2
let_7a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	12066	-16.70	TGCTGGACAACAGGCAACCTTA : : : TTGATATGTTG - GATGATGGAGT	9.78E-2
let_7a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	16253	-13.10	TTCTTTGCAATTCACAGACTTCA : : : TTGATATGTTGGATG - ATGGAGT	1.78E-1
let_7a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	18101	-16.20	CAC - AGGCA - CCTACACACTCA : TTGATATGTTGGATG - ATGGAGT	1.69E-1
let_7a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	18494	-12.50	TTATGTACAAGGACTTCCTTG : : TTGATATGTTGGATGATGGAGT	9.48E-2
mir_101_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	7608	-12.60	ACAATTGGAATTGTGTAATTG : : TCGTAGTCGTGACACTATTGAC	4.38E-2
mir_101_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	29501	-13.10	TCCATGAGCA - -GTGCTGACTC : TCGTAGTCGTGACACTATTGAC	6.68E-2
mir_124_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	4430	-12.10	ATGCCTGCTG - TGTGGAACT : : TAGTCCAGGGACACTTGTGC	2E-3
mir_126_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	19813	-15.90	CCAGTACCAGAGGTGAAAATA : : : GCGCATGGTTTCATTATTAC	2.35E-1
mir_145_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	12049	-13.40	CAAGCTTTGTGAAGAAATGCTGGAC : : TCCCTAAGGAC - CCTT - TGACCTG	9.78E-2
mir_145_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	15188	-12.70	GAGGAGCTACTGTAGTAATTGGAA : : TCCCT - AAGACCCCTTTTGACCTG	1.4E-1
mir_145_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22091	-14.30	ATGGA - CCTTGAAGAAAACAGGGT : : TCCCTAAGGAC - -CCTTTGACCTG	1.24E-1
mir_145_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22789	-18.90	AATCGCTCCAGGGCAAATGGAA TCCCTAAGGACCTTTTGACCTG	2.78E-1
mir_15a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	7628	-15.30	TGTGATACATTGTGCTGGTA : GTGTTGGTAATACACGACGAT	4.38E-2
mir_15a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	8445	-19.50	AACAAATACGTA - GTGCTGCTA : GTGTTGGTAATACACGACGAT	1.3E-1
mir_15a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	14018	-12.10	GTGATGCCATGCGAAATGCTGGTA : GTGTTGGTA - -ATACACGACGAT	1.06E-1
mir_15a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	14639	-13.20	CACCTACTA - ACAATGTTGCTT : : GTGTTGGTAATACACGACGAT	3.2E-1
mir_15a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	19463	-14.70	CACGTTGCAATTAGTGGTGCTG : : :	2.42E-1

miR Name	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
				GTGT - TTG - GTAATACACGACGAT	
mir_15a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	23607	-13.90	GGCGGGCACGTA - GTGTAGCTA : :: GTGTTGGTAATACACGACGAT	1.26E-1
mir_15a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	26707	-13.20	TAGCTTGTTTTGTGCTTGCTGCTG : GTGTTGGTAATAC - -ACGACGAT	3.29E-1
mir_15b_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	7744	-13.50	TGTTACAGTGAAGATGGTTCC ATCTCGTGTATTACTAAGC	1.52E-1
mir_15b_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	29432	-13.20	AAGAAACAGCAAACGTGACTCT : ATCT - CGTGTATTACTAAGC	2.36E-2
mir_15b_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	7628	-17.70	TGTGATACATTCTGTCTGGTA : ACATTGGTACTACACGACGAT	4.38E-2
mir_15b_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	9839	-14.20	AAGTTGCGTAGTGTGTCTATTA : : : ACATTTG - -GTACTACACGACGAT	1.18E-1
mir_15b_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	9934	-12.10	AACTAGCTACAGAGAAGCTGCTT : : ACATTTGGT - ACTACACGACGAT	2.32E-1
mir_15b_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	14017	-17.40	TGTGATGCCATGCGAAATGCTGGTA : ACATT - TGGTAC - -TACACGACGAT	1.06E-1
mir_15b_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	16270	-15.20	ACTTCATTAAGATGTTGCTT : ACATTTGGTACTACACGACGAT	1.78E-1
mir_15b_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	26712	-14.30	TGT - -TTTGTG - CTTGCTGCTG : ACATTTGGTACTACACGACGAT	3.29E-1
mir_16_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	173	-14.52	CGTCTACTTCTGCAGGCTGCTT : GGCG - TTATAAATGCACGACGAT	1.28E-1
mir_16_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	8445	-15.20	AACAAATACGTA - GTGTGCTA GGCGTTATAAATGCACGACGAT	1.3E-1
mir_16_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	9568	-12.40	ACCTGGTGTAT - -TCTGTTA : : GGCGTTATAAATGCACGACGAT	2.05E-1
mir_16_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	19465	-16.50	CGTTGCAATTAGTGTGCTG : GGCGTTATAAATGCACGACGAT	2.42E-1
mir_16_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	23606	-12.94	CGCGGGCACGTA - GTGTAGCTA : GGCGTTATAAATGCACGACGAT	1.26E-1
mir_16_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	28925	-13.70	GCTCTGCTTTGC - TGCTGCTT GGCGTTATAAATGCACGACGAT	4.64E-2
mir_200a_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	5287	-13.20	TTATC - TTGCCACTGCATTGTTA : : TGTAGCAATGGT - CTGT CACAAT	1.62E-1

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mir_200a_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	11321	-12.30	GCATC--AGCT-G-TAGTGTTA : : : : TGAGCAATGGTCTGTCCAAAT	2.46E-1
mir_200a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	11350	-14.70	GACAGCAAGAACTGTGTATGATG : AGGTCGTGACAGGC-CATTCTAC	9.19E-2
mir_200a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22795	-18.50	TCCAGGGCAAACGGAAAGATT : : AGGTCGTGACAGGCCATTCTAC	2.78E-1
mir_200b_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22795	-14.30	TCCAGGGCAAACGGAAAGATT : AGGTTACGACGGGTCACTCTAC	2.78E-1
mir_205_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	12847	-18.30	TAGATCCCTAAGAGTGATGGA : : GTCTGAGGCCACCTACTTCCT	2.9E-1
mir_205_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	25435	-12.10	TTGAAGCAAGGTGAAATCAAGGA GTCTGAG-GCCACCTACTTCCT	3.48E-1
mir_205_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	28897	-13.90	TAGA--ATGGCTGGCAATGGCGGT : : : GTCTGAGGCC-ACC-TTACTTCCT	6.4E-3
mir_21_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	5907	-14.20	CTTATAAATTGGATGGTGTG : TGCGGGTAGTGACCACAAC	2.98E-1
mir_21_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	9234	-15.10	AAAGATCAGAAGCTGGTGTGTT : TGCGGGTAGTGACCACAAC	3.03E-1
mir_21_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	14478	-14.60	CCACTTCAGAGAGTAGTGTGTTG : TGCGGGTAGCT-GA-CCACAAC	1.22E-1
mir_21_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22329	-14.00	CAGGTTGGACAGCTGGTGCTG : :: : : TGCGGGTAGTGACCACAAC	6.11E-2
mir_21_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	23053	-17.30	CCAACCCA-CTAATGGTGTG TGCGGGTAGTGACCACAAC	5.13E-2
mir_29a_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	16268	-13.40	AGACTTCATTAAGATGTGGTCTT : : ATTGGCTAAAGTCT--ACCACGAT	1.78E-1
mir_29a_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22326	-16.20	CTTCAGGTTGGACAGCTGGTGCTG : : ATTGGCTAA--AGTCTACCACGAT	6.11E-2
mir_29a_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	28626	-17.20	AAGCTGGACTCCCTATGGTGCTA : : : ATTGGCT-AAAG-TCTACCACGAT	2.98E-1
mir_29a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	2942	-15.50	CTGGCATTGATTTAGATGAGT :: : : GACTTGTGGTTTCTTTAGTCA	1.57E-1
mir_29a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	17619	-12.20	TAAAGCACATAAGACAATCAGC : : GACTTGTG--GTTTCTTTAGTCA	3.34E-1
mir_29a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	22091	-15.20	ATGGACCTTGAAGAAAACAGG : : :	1.24E-1

miR Name	transcript name	leftmost position of predicted target site	folding energy (in -Kcal/mol)	heteroduplex	p value
mir_34a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	17308	-12.70	TGTAAT-GTAAATGCATTGCCT : : : : TGTTGGTCGATTCTGTGACGGT	9.05E-2
mir_34a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	25338	-17.00	ACGACT--CTGAGCCAGTGCTC : : : : TGTTGGTCGATTCTGTGACGGT	3.25E-1
mir_34a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	26043	-14.90	TCAATTGAGTACAGACACTGGTG :: : : TGTTGG-TCGATTCTGTGACGGT	5.05E-2
mir_34a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	28888	-13.70	TTCTCCTGCTA-GAATGGCTGGCA : TGTTGGTCGATTCT--GTGACGGT	6.4E-3
mir_34a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	29497	-15.20	ACAATC-CATGAG-CAGTGCTG : : : TGTTGGTCGATTCTGTGACGGT	6.68E-2
mir_34a_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	29768	-21.20	ACAAT--GCTAGGGAGAGCTGCCT : : : : TGTTGGTCGATTCT--GTGACGGT	3.52E-1
mir_98_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	9845	-12.20	CGTAGTGATGTGCT-ATTACCTCT : : : : : TTGTTAT--GTTGAATGATGGAGT	1.18E-1
mir_98_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	12066	-13.30	TGCTGGACAACAGGGCAACTTA : : : TTGTTATGTTG-AATGATGGAGT	9.78E-2
mir_98_5p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	18465	-12.10	TGGAGATCAATTTAAACACTCA : TTGTTATGTTGAAT-GATGGAGT	9.48E-2
mir_99a_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	3066	-12.50	GTGATTGTGAAGAAGAGATTG : : GTCTGG-GTATCTTC-GCTCGAAC	8.61E-3
mir_99a_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	8104	-12.70	TGCAACTGCAGAAGCTGAACCTG : GTCTGGGTATCTCG-CTCGAAC	6.2E-2
mir_99a_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	9298	-14.20	CAGATCTTACCAG-GAGTTTT : : : GTCTGGGTATCTCGCTCGAAC	4.38E-2
mir_99a_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	24038	-12.80	GTGACACTGCAGATGCTGGCTTC : : GTCTG-GG-TATCTTCGCTCGAAC	1.04E-1
mir_99a_3p	NC_045512.2 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 isolate Wuhan_Hu_1, complete genome	24601	-16.00	TAGAGCTGCAGAAATCAGAGCTTC : : GTCTGGGTATCTT--CGCTCGAAC	1.42E-1

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